

Possibilities of Entrepreneurship Development in Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the characteristics of the factors, the presence and interaction of which makes it possible to create conditions for effective entrepreneurial activity. At the same time, great importance was attached to the factor of the development of market infrastructure, whose effective and comprehensive development, in the author's opinion, is one of the fundamental factors in the successful development of entrepreneurial activity.

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, factors, property, market economy, investment environment, guarantees of independence.*

Introduction

In the conditions of the formation and development of market relations, one of the priority areas of economic reforms was the development of entrepreneurship, because, which were developed in the early 90s, through the lease, redemption of enterprises into collective and other forms of ownership, as a logical continuation of the simplest forms of economic management, the formation of this basis of entrepreneurship in its various forms was facilitated by the development of a socially oriented market economy.

The maximum freedom of an economic entity, which is an entrepreneur, full responsibility for the results of economic activity with legal equality of all forms of ownership allows to realize the abilities of each person, increases his business economic activity, opens up new opportunities for using the achievements of science and technology. The most urgent need for this is in all spheres of the economy.

Let us consider some of the reasons for this phenomenon, firstly, the significantly overestimated investment demand is chronically not provided with material and technical resources and in recent years the balance has been increasing.

Secondly, there is an obvious discrepancy between the desired maximum production volume and the monetary resources that do not meet these needs. Hence the desire by any means to "squeeze" the object into subsidies as a result - unprofitableness.

Thirdly, the structure of investments is difficult to rebuild for social facilities, reconstruction and modernization. In addition, the seeming cheapness of products is ruinous for the country due to the low quality and technical backwardness of products. Product quality is still lagging behind the required level. It is no coincidence that researchers point to the urgent need to strengthen the focus of the state export policy to stimulate production and supply to the world market of high-quality products with high added value [4]. Today, due to the careless use of precious economic resources, the specific consumption of products per unit of national income is approximately twice the indicators of countries with market economies. At the same time, there was a decrease in the price of housing and social and cultural facilities.

Hence, the question of the accelerated creation of the necessary conditions for the comprehensive development of market relations, and the promotion of the early introduction of entrepreneurship in all spheres of the economy is raised with all certainty. It is reasonably assumed that the transition to market relations in the investment complex will occur at a faster pace due to the greater structural mobility of the sphere and services, which have a certain entrepreneurial experience, less than in the industry of monopolization.

Related Work

Naturally, these and other emerging problems are completely new. Their study is connected not simply with the creation of any prerequisites for achieving the next momentary results in increasing the efficiency of work, notes J.R. Zaynalov and S.S. Alieva. The task should be set in principle: to get a qualitative leap, a breakthrough in the functioning of the investment sphere [3].

The result of the transformation should be a growing acceleration of investment turnover. For this, along with capital investments, we need a production base to encourage entrepreneurship, new market relations, and free pricing. At the same time, the task is to balance the market by means of budgetary, tax and credit policies. S. Turabekov and M. Muhammedov believes that the cheapening of banking services, further simplification and unification of relations between business structures and banks are of great importance for the development of entrepreneurship in the country [5].

It becomes vitally necessary to comprehensively study the essence and features of the development of entrepreneurship in all spheres of the economy in the context of the development of market relations on the scale of an economically administrative territory, which is the Samarkand region, which has a sufficiently developed industrial complex.

As noted by J.R. Zaynalov and S.S. Alieva, today it is necessary to recognize that the problem of the development of entrepreneurship in industry, its role in improving the efficiency of the industrial complex as a whole in a market economy is practically not disclosed by economic theory, there are no methodological foundations for the formation and life of small business, promising directions of this work are not substantiated [3]. In the available works, only certain aspects of the problem are disclosed, the recommendations are often very general in nature, not taking into account the specifics of the industry or service sector.

Discussion

This is partly understandable. In the conditions of a market economy, we do not live long enough, it continues to form and develop. Hence the complete lack of experience, necessary theoretical knowledge. The legal framework for the formation of market relations has not been fully determined, only at the end of 2017 the status of entrepreneurship was established, thanks to the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2]. There is practically no mechanism for the

formation of business structures. But at the same time, it should be noted that questions remain about the mechanisms and essence of the formation of the product market, its interdependence on the functioning of the market infrastructure of other sectors of the national economy.

It seems, in this regard, to answer the question of what are the necessary and sufficient conditions for the formation and development of entrepreneurship, to determine the role and responsibility of local authorities in the implementation of the processes of demonopolization, denationalization, privatization, social protection of both producers of products and consumers.

Unfortunately, it must be admitted that the long-term disregard for the specifics of commodity production and the role of the market has led to the fact that the current generation of economic leaders, for the most part, does not possess the necessary theoretical base at all and does not have any practical experience of working on the principles of economic independence of enterprises. Most of today's managers and specialists are not familiar with the methods of picking a portfolio of orders, setting up production, distribution and marketing of products focused on consumer needs, very roughly imagine activities in competition with other enterprises. And this circumstance, to a certain extent, can become an obstacle to the development of entrepreneurship. It will take some time to eliminate it, to create the necessary prerequisites, including legislative ones.

In modern domestic practice, the concept of entrepreneurship is legally defined [1]. Now, according to the law, under entrepreneurial activity (entrepreneurship) is an initiative activity carried out by subjects of entrepreneurial activity in accordance with the legislation, aimed at obtaining income (profit) at their own risk and under their property responsibility within the limits determined by the organizational and legal form of the enterprise (Art. 3).

Somewhat unsuccessfully, from our point of view, the law singles out only the function of earning income (profit). It is hardly worth emphasizing, especially since Article 11 of the law establishes that the subject has the right to independently form the production program; choose suppliers and consumers of their products (works, services) and receive income (profit) from entrepreneurship in an unlimited amount.

True, what if the subject consists of one business person?

In fairness, it should be noted that you should not pretend that an entrepreneur will not work hard for only one public good. This, as we have seen, is almost impossible to achieve, but it is probably wrong to focus on profit as well. These interests must be combined.

Essentially, subjects of entrepreneurial activity can be legal entities and individual entrepreneurs who are not limited in their legal capacity, as well as associations of individual entrepreneurs of joint entrepreneurship. It is also allowed to engage in entrepreneurial activities for citizens of foreign states and stateless persons, within the framework established by law. It follows from this that any person or group of persons not deprived of the right of legal capacity, and in certain cases citizens of other states, can create an enterprise, for which it is enough to register it in the prescribed manner in order to obtain the status of an entrepreneur.

Meanwhile, it should be noted that for the implementation of economic activities, an entrepreneur is allowed to use hired labor. Moreover, the entrepreneur has the opportunity not to be involved in managing the subject. For this, a manager (manager) can be used, who, according to a contract that defines the obligations of the parties, performs his functions.

The guarantees of independence, independence of the subject, its protection from the state and other diktat are, in our opinion, the fundamental legal norm that provides the most important prerequisite

for the development and formation of entrepreneurship. Not only economic, scientific, technical and legal support for entrepreneurial activity, the possibility of insuring entrepreneurial risk is guaranteed, but also land and property taxes are provided.

Conclusion

The most important provisions of the financial policy of the state in relation to the entrepreneur, with his full independence, are for the first time determined by our legislation. Providing a very important aspect of successful entrepreneurial activity: not only not to interfere, not to interfere, but also to help in every possible way, contribute, and if necessary, save an entrepreneur who is in a difficult financial situation.

Comprehensively considering the nature of the development and interaction of factors of market relations, it is necessary to determine as priority those aspects that are directly aimed at creating conditions for the successful development of entrepreneurship, should objectively contribute to increasing the efficiency of all spheres of the economy.

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